

**PARTIYAVIYLIK TIZIMINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARINI
O‘RGANISH VA TASNIFLASH**

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola sog‘lom demokratiya uchun muhim bo‘lgan partiyaviy tizimga bag‘ishlangan bo‘lib, u hukumat va xalq o‘rtasida vositachi bo‘lib, fuqarolarning siyosiy jarayonlarda ishtirok etishiga imkon beradi. Tadqiqotchilar partiya tizimlariga turli xil ta’riflar beradilar, ba’zilari esa partiyalar, davlat va jamiyat o‘rtasidagi munosabatlarga e’tibor qaratadilar. Ushbu maqolada partiyaviy tizimlarning tasnifi turli yondashuvlar yordamida miqdoriy va sifat xususiyatlarini tahlil qiluvchi global siyosatshunoslarning e’tiborini tortdi. Rossiyalik siyosatshunos L.N. Alisova partiya tizimini muayyan faoliyat va siyosiy qadriyatlarga qarashga ega bo‘lgan o‘zaro bog‘langan partiyalar yig‘indisi deb biladi. Fransuz tadqiqotchisi M.Dyuverjer partiyaviy tizim deganda vaqt o‘tishi bilan ittifoqlar va qarama-qarshiliklar tuzadigan mamlakat ichidagi barqaror partiyalar ansambli deb ta’riflaydi. Ikkala nuqtai nazar ham partiya tizimining rivojlanishini belgilashda barqarorlik muhimligini ta’kidlaydi. Partiyaviy tizimlarning turli tasniflari siyosatshunoslikda taniqli siyosatshunoslar tomonidan taklif etiladi. Muallif partiya tizimi tipologiyasini tushunishga oid bir qancha yondashuvlarni tahlil qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar. Siyosiy jarayon, partiyaviy tizim, siyosiy qadriyatlar, o‘z-o‘zini tashkil etish, funkcionallik, siyosiy raqobat, fuqarolik jamiyati.

**THE CURRENT STATE AND PROBLEMS OF STUDYING THE CONCEPT AND
CLASSIFICATION OF THE PARTY SYSTEM**

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Annotation. *The article is devoted to the party system which is essential for a healthy democracy as it serves as a mediator between the government and the people, allowing citizens to engage in the political process. Researchers have varying definitions of party systems, with some focusing on relationships between parties, the state, and society. In this article, the classification of party systems has gained attention from political scientists globally, who analyze quantitative and qualitative characteristics using different approaches. Russian political scientist L.N. Alisova sees the party system as a set of interconnected parties with specific activities and views on political values. French researcher M. Duverger defines a party system as a stable ensemble of parties within a country that form alliances and oppositions over time. Both perspectives highlight the importance of stability in defining a party system’s development. Different classifications of party systems are proposed by well-known political scientists in political science. The author analyzes several approaches to the understanding of party system typology.*

Key words. *Political process, party system, political values, self-organization, functionalism, political competition, civil society.*

СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ПОНЯТИЯ И КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ ПАРТИЙНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

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***Аннотация.** Статья посвящена партийной системе, которая необходима для здоровой демократии, поскольку она служит посредником между правительством и народом, позволяя гражданам участвовать в политическом процессе. Исследователи дают разные определения партийным системам, некоторые из которых фокусируются на отношениях между партиями, государством и обществом. В этой статье классификация партийных систем привлекла внимание политологов во всем мире, которые анализируют количественные и качественные характеристики, используя разные подходы. Российский политолог Л. Н. Алисова рассматривает партийную систему как совокупность взаимосвязанных партий с определенными видами деятельности и взглядами на политические ценности. Французский исследователь М. Дюверже определяет партийную систему как устойчивый ансамбль партий внутри страны, которые со временем формируют альянсы и оппозиции. Обе точки зрения подчеркивают важность стабильности в определении развития партийной системы. Известные политологи в политологии предлагают различные классификации партийных систем. Автор анализирует несколько подходов к пониманию типологии партийных систем.*

***Ключевые слова.** Политический процесс, партийная система, политические ценности, самоорганизация, функционализм, политическая конкуренция, гражданское общество.*

INTRODUCTION.

A well-functioning party system is a crucial component of a healthy democracy. Parties serve as mediators between the government and the people, providing a platform for citizens to engage in the political process and express their preferences. They help to organize political competition, facilitate the formation of policies, and hold elected officials accountable for their actions. The stronger the

political ideology of a political party, the stronger its position in the political life of the state and society.

As the American sociologist, and founder of the school of structural functionalism T. Parsons argued, politics is one of the subsystems of society and it is closely related to the function of achieving goals¹. In the political sphere, not only the function of public administration is realized, but also the interests of the people, which is largely facilitated by political parties. As a form of self-organization of the population within the framework of civil society, parties help citizens achieve goals determined by their interests and beliefs, and provide an opportunity to solve pressing problems through active political participation.

In the Uzbek and foreign scientific tradition, basic views on the essence of the party system, genesis, functions and roles have already been formed. But since the role and activities of political parties in the political life of society do not remain constant, it seems necessary, after analyzing the common classifications of party systems, to identify those that should be used most effectively in further studies of the party systems of specific states, including when conducting a comparative analysis.

Many researchers and political scientists have expressed their opinions about the party system. However, even today, there is no unified and universally recognized definition of the party system. Therefore, it is appropriate to pay attention to the definitions of many political scientists and sociologists who have defined the party system.

The very definition of “**party system**” under consideration includes both the relationship of parties with the state, and the relationship of both parties among themselves and with the society to which they address as part of the political struggle for power. Moreover, it also makes it possible to analyze the characteristics of the perturbations experienced by society.

¹ Парсонс Т. О социальных системах. М., 2002. –С.568.
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Over the course of recent times, the issue of party systems has become a key object of research for many political scientists from around the world. It was analyzed, quantitative and qualitative characteristics were examined using different approaches, identified as a separate object of study, or, conversely, relationships were found with other components of the political system.

Russian political scientist L.N. Alisova characterizes the party system as a political structure consisting of “a set of political parties of various types with their strong connections and relationships among themselves, with the state and other institutions of power, character, conditions of activity, views on the basic values of the political culture of society and the degree of consistency of these views in the implementation of their accepted ideological doctrines, forms, and methods of practical political activity”². In fact, the party system, according to this position, is divided into parties and their connections with other elements of the political system.

A classic of political sociology, a French researcher of parties and party systems, M. Duverger defines the party system as follows: “In each country, over a more or less long period, the number of parties, their internal structure, their ideology, their relative sizes, their alliances, their types of opposition acquire certain stability. This stable ensemble forms a system of parties”³. For Duverger, the main factor is the stability of the existence of the “party ensemble”, which allows us to talk about the development of a system.

The famous Polish scientist E. Wiert considers the party system as a set of relations between legally operating political parties. These relationships are expressed in rivalry or in a joint struggle for power⁴. It is noteworthy that the Wiert does not include in the party system either state institutions, non-party interest groups or other organizations of this kind acting on behalf of society.

In this sense, Russian political scientist T.V. Shmachkova writes: “The party system is understood as a political configuration made up of a set of independent

² Алисова Л.Н. Партийная система // Политическая энциклопедия: в 2 т. М., 2019. –С.2.

³ Дюверже М. Политические партии. М., 2000. –С.29.

⁴ Вятр Е. Социология политических отношений / под ред. Ф.М. Бурлацкого. М., 2013. –С.123.

elements and determined by the number and parameters of the parties existing in it. This concept determines today the essence of political regimes and serves as the basis for their classification. The party system itself is determined by two criteria - one takes into account the number of parties included in it, the other - their parameters, which helps to distinguish between the forms of a multi-party system”⁵.

According to the abovementioned definitions, the party system is a set of parties that exist in a particular state and form a certain configuration within the political system, remaining unchanged for a more or less long time.

MAIN PART.

Understanding the phenomenon of party systems is facilitated by their classification. Political scientists have proposed various options, which are based on certain characteristics and principles that separate some party systems from others.

Dutch political scientist G. Daalder studied party systems through the concept of “center,” that is, the middle from the point of view of division into left and right⁶. He identified several types of party systems:

- 1) two-party system (example - Great Britain);
- 2) a system of two and a half parties (for example - Germany);
- 3) a party system, where a large party is opposed by several smaller and smaller parties (examples: Ireland, Sweden);
- 4) two-bloc party system (examples - Denmark, France);
- 5) a party system with constant (frequent) rule of one or a group of parties, changing its allies from time to time (examples - the Netherlands, Italy, and, in a sense, Finland);
- 6) party system of minority governments;
- 7) party system of unstable coalitions (example of Iceland)⁷.

⁵ Шмачкова Т.В. Из основ политологии Запада // Полис. 2022. № 2. С. 133-145.

⁶ Daalder H. In search of the center of European party systems // American political science review. Washington, 2016. Vol. 78, № 1. P. 92-109.

⁷ Daalder H., Mair P. Western European Party Systems. Beverly Hills, 2018. –P.38.

There are several approaches to the typology of party systems in modern political science. It differs depending on the basis of classification based on its most characteristic features. The typology developed by the most prominent researcher of political parties, Maurice Duverger, and implemented on a quantitative basis, is the most famous and widespread. Based on the number of parties that actually operate in the society and participate in the struggle for power or its implementation, he emphasizes three types of party systems: two-party system, multi-party system, and one-party system⁸.

Combining qualitative and quantitative criteria for determining a party system, Italian political scientist G. Sartori proposed his own classification:

- 1) party system with one party (Albania, former USSR);
- 2) a system with a party exercising hegemony (Mexico);
- 3) system with a dominant party (Japan, India);
- 4) two-party system of simple pluralism (USA, UK, Canada);
- 5) system of limited pluralism (Belgium, Germany);
- 6) a system of extreme pluralism (Italy, the Netherlands, Finland);
- 7) atomized system (Malaysia)⁹.

According to him, the system of “moderate pluralism” consists of three to five competing parties. They create a coalition government. Six or more parties is a polarized system with a huge ideological difference between the parties and the resulting political tension.

R.Zh. Schwarzenberg based the typology of party systems on a unique scale for reducing competition between parties:

- 1) multi-party systems: complete multi-party system; moderate multi-party system;
- 2) two-party systems: imperfect two-party system; perfect two-party system;
- 3) systems with a dominant party: dominant party; super-dominant party¹⁰.

⁸ Дюверже М. Политические партии. М., 2000. –С.162.

⁹ Sartory G. Parties and Party Systems // Framework for analysis. N.Y., 1976. Vol. 1. P. 122-179.

¹⁰ Шварценберг Р.-Ж. Политическая социология: в 3 ч. М., 1992. –С.52.

Thus, there are many approaches to defining the concept of a party system, studying its dynamics and formation, and various classifications of party systems have been proposed. To analyze party systems, including comparative analysis, it seems optimal to use the following universal definitions of party systems: one-party, system with a dominant party, two-party, moderate pluralism, extreme pluralism, atomized, one-and-a-half party, two-and-a-half party system, party system with government one or a group of parties that constantly change their allies.

The existing definitions and classifications, however, do not allow us to fully assess the effectiveness of a particular model of the party system in a certain state. In any case, the actual configuration of the party system should be considered in the context of a variety of processes - democratization, political struggle, coordination of interests within the very party system of a certain state, designed to adequately respond to signals from the external environment.

It is not always the quantitative characteristics that should be taken as a basis when there are attempts to exclude qualitative pluralism, the stable existence of the system over a long period, or the representation of the systemic opposition in parliament. Often, a small number of batches is enough to achieve the listed characteristics. For example, the United States and Great Britain have established two-party models, and these states have democratic traditions dating back several centuries of their sovereign existence. It is in a two-party system that each party tries to expand its electoral base as much as possible, and in a system with a dominant party, the ruling political force does not face the need to sacrifice some provision of its program for the sake of the need to merge into a coalition with other parties.

Consequently, in addition to the quantitative characteristics of party systems, much attention should be paid to their qualitative measurement, which is more indicative of many aspects of the scientific issues under consideration. Then the definition of party systems and the concepts of their classifications will receive an additional empirical basis, showing the effectiveness of a specific model about the country in which it exists.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, the concept and classification of party systems are crucial in understanding the dynamics of politics in a democratic society. The party system serves as a framework for organizing political competition and representation, providing citizens with choices and opportunities to participate in the political process. By analyzing the number of parties, their ideological positions, and their relationships with one another, we can gain insights into the level of competition, polarization, and stability within a political system.

The classification of party systems into categories such as two-party systems, multi-party systems, dominant-party systems, and one-party systems helps us understand the diversity and complexity of political landscapes around the world. Each type of party system has its own strengths and weaknesses, influencing the functioning of democracy and governance in different ways.

Finally, studying party systems provides valuable insights into the nature of political competition, representation, and power distribution within a society. It allows us to analyze trends in voter behavior, government formation, policy-making processes, and the overall health of democracy. By deepening our understanding of party systems, we can better navigate the complexities of modern politics and work towards building more inclusive and responsive political institutions.

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